

ISic3469

I.Sicily inscription 3469

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance

Victoria, found in a private house

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Victoria, Gozo, Museo archeologico nazionale (Cittadella)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR112580

1. Cereri Íuliae Augustae
2. Divi Augustí matri
3. Ti (beri) Caesaris Augusti
4. Lutatia C (ai) f (ilia) sacerdos Augustae
5. Imp (eratoris) perpet (ui) uxor
6. M (arci) Lívi M (arci) f (ili) Qui (rina) Optati flaminis G[a]u!(itanorum)
7. Iuliae Augusti Imp (eratoris) perpet (ui) cum V
8. líberis s (ua) p (ecunia) consecravít.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285176
EDR 112580
EDCS 22100620

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